

**A Comparative study of Multiple Intelligence of Tribal and Non-Tribal Secondary School Students of Karbi
Anglong with regards to Gender***Ms. Bibori Baglary¹ & Dr Mallika Kalita²*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17497171>**Review: 01/10/2025,****Acceptance: 12/10/2025****Published: 01/11/2025**

Abstract: Every individual is unique with regards to intelligence. Howard Gardner, a developmental psychologist said that human being has nine types of intelligence which are Visual-spatial, Linguistic-verbal, Logical-mathematical, Body-Kinesthetic, Musical, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal, Naturalistic intelligence and Existential intelligence known as Multiple Intelligence. Gardner explained in his theory that all individuals possess different kinds of intelligence and accordingly students perform differently. The main aim of this study is to compare the Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal students and also to assess if there is any difference of boys and girls of secondary level students. Though tribal communities are the most indigenous habitant of India, but it has been observed in many situations that tribal people have been remained backward for centuries in many aspects. Therefore, an attempt is undertaken to discuss about the Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal students at secondary schools. A Standardized Multiple Intelligence Scale (MIS-ASPS) developed by Surbhi Agarwal and Suraksha Pal is employed as research tool for collecting data. For the data treatment, simple %, Mean, Standard Deviation and t- test are used. In this study the researcher used descriptive survey research method and stratified random sampling procedure for selecting students' sample to collect relevant data.

Keywords- Gender, Intelligence, Multiple Intelligence, Non-Tribal and Tribal.

Introduction: Human Intelligence is the ability or mental capacity with the help of which people acquire different kinds of knowledge from this world. It is because of intelligence people are able to solve or recognize various kinds of problems. It is also defined how human being learn from experiences, learn quickly, think abstractly, understand and can deal with different situations. Every human being has their own ways to learn, to express their feelings, strength and potential ability. Human intelligence is a mental quality that consists of the abilities to learn from different experiences, adapt to new situations, understand and handle abstract concepts and use knowledge to manipulate one's environment (Sternberg, 2023). In Multiple Intelligence theory, Gardner identified that each individual has different learning style, methods and techniques and acquire information according to their own innate capacities. Gardner recognized that individuals have non-identical intelligence and believed intelligence is definite and specific while being working with normal and gifted children and brain-damaged adults. Howard Gardner, a developmental psychologist developed Multiple Intelligence theory by research and observation in 1970 and 1980. He presented the theory in 1983 for the first time in a book "Frames of Mind" where he traced the theory of Multiple Intelligence. Gardner identified and outlined that there are seven different types of human intelligence which are Visual-spatial, Linguistic-verbal, Logical-mathematical, Body-kinesthetic, Musical, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal and later in 1993 he added two more intelligence which are Naturalistic intelligence and Existential intelligence. Gardner stated that traditional concept of intelligence is too confined where other intelligence is not measured while measuring the IQ of students. He said that human being has many types of intelligence and learning takes place through its different kinds. In his theory, Gardner suggested to empower learners and not confined them to learn single entity. He said that learners never learn at the same tempo or never learn equally from the same experiences since everyone is dominated by different component of intelligence as per his theory.

Karbi Anglong district is an autonomous district of Assam under sixth schedule of Indian constitution. This district is unique from its natural set up geographically surrounded by Mikir hills and political administration is in the hands of local tribal people (mainly Karbi tribe). Generally, in India tribal people are said to be the backward section and in Assam, people belonging to Karbi tribe are said to be more backward in comparison to other tribes. In Indian constitution also tribal people are considered as the most backward among other sections in the community. In the Constitution, the status of Scheduled Tribe (ST) is given to help backward communities to improve their social and economic conditions and ensure that they are included in mainstream society by giving them equal

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opportunities of education by government. It is because they have limited access to proper quality education and various challenges like, healthcare, employment, economic resources, poor infrastructure, cultural barriers etc. In a study on the educational institutions in Karbi Anglong District, Assam, aiming to assess their current status it was found that the district has a scarcity of educational facilities. It also highlighted the urgent need for strategic planning and establishment of better educational institutions in the region. The study emphasized on the importance of collaboration between open-minded individuals, vigilant citizens and Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) to enhance the conditions of education. (Mochahari et al., 2021). Research has shown that there are differences in intelligence between tribal and non-tribal people (Choudhury & Talukdar, 2021). It was stated that non-tribal adolescents' emotional intelligence was higher than tribal adolescents. The gender wise finding was that boys' emotional intelligence was found to be higher than girls. One study found that non-tribal students showed higher levels of self-concept (SC) than tribal students, while tribal students showed a higher level of emotional intelligence (EI) than non-tribal students (Sultana & Islam, 2024). A study has found that government school students exhibit higher levels of multiple intelligence compared to private schools. Additionally, girls tend to show greater multiple intelligence levels than boys in three areas: logical, interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence. On the other hand, boys showed better strength in spiritual and naturalistic intelligence than girls (Anitha et al., 2013). Another study also revealed that there is a difference in multiple intelligence levels with regards to gender showing that girls exhibit higher levels of multiple intelligence compared to boys (Laxman, 2018).

India is changing towards its development in all the field such as science and technology, agriculture, education, infrastructure, sports, social sector, health, politics etc. Tribal people also want to be developed like non-tribal people in all spheres of existence of life. But still in some rural or interior areas of Assam, particularly in Karbi Anglong district majority of the tribal people are backward. But from general observations, at present in many situations no such differences are seen among tribal and non-tribal people in normal social and academic situations. Therefore, present study is carried out to check the status of multiple intelligence level between Tribal and Non-tribal students with regards to gender in Karbi Anglong district of Assam.

Significance of the study

Earlier, intelligence was defined as a human capacity that is primarily concerned with problem solving skills, logical and critical thinking skills and associated to academic fields only. But modern psychologist Gardener says that Intelligence is the capacity of an individual to showcase and perform in different field. People cannot say that someone has no intelligence or zero intelligence. Some may have good observation power, effective communication skill, ability to solve, logical analysis capacity whereas some others may have strong physique, high musical aptitude to sing and remember musical pattern, understand emotions and feelings of others. Tribal people also may have these innate qualities but due to various reasons they don't have awareness of their talents, couldn't get proper knowledge and education. Many factors such as Socio-economic problems, lack of facilities, superstitions, lack of communication, religious challenges etc., are the main obstacles of the people in Assam, particularly with the tribal people of Karbi-Anglong district. People often complain that tribal communities in Assam are not getting sufficient scope for development because of which huge talents of the region are going for wastage instead of making them human resources. Previous researches have shown that if facilities are provided related to all the dimension of Multiple Intelligence, then tribal students can definitely enhance their overall performance in various fields of the society in large.

Generally, people say that boys possess higher intelligence than girls since boys are given preference in all decision- making process of a society. But, to check whether it is true or not, means to study whether gender has a role in Multiple intelligence or not, an effort is taken to study on this variable. Therefore, the present study makes an attempt to study the level of Multiple Intelligence and also tries to promote students' awareness of multiple intelligence. Hence, it is expected that present study will help the secondary level students to explore their various abilities as well as other inborn potentials mentioned in Gardener's theory. It will help the sampled group to make decision on their future career in their lives, choose career what they actually want to be as per capacity. Accordingly, present study is supposed to be very significant.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of tribal students with regards to gender.

- ii. To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of non-tribal students with regards to gender.
- iii. To compare the Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal school students in Karbi-Anglong district of Assam.
- iv. To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of all boys of secondary school students in Karbi Anglong district.
- v. To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of all girls of secondary school students.
- vi. To find out the difference in Multiple Intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students in Karbi Anglong district of Assam.

Research hypotheses

H₀1. There exists no significant mean difference between tribal and non-tribal students' Multiple Intelligence at secondary level.

H₀2. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between tribal boys and non-tribal boys.

H₀3. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between tribal girls and non-tribal girls students at secondary level.

H₀4. There exists no significant mean difference between boys and girls Multiple Intelligence at secondary level.

Operational Definitions

Tribal: Tribal are referred as Scheduled Tribes people according to Article 366 (25) of the Constitution of India. Scheduled Tribes are defined as the groups or parts of tribal communities, that are officially recognized under Article 342. In the present study, Tribal refers to the students belonging to Karbi and Bodo students of Karbi Anglong District, Assam.

Non-Tribal: In the present study, non-tribal refers to those students who don't belong to any tribe.

Gender: Gender refers to male and female students in the present study.

Delimitations of the study

- (i) The present study is delimited to Government Provincial zed Secondary schools of East Karbi Anglong district of Assam only. The researcher has taken up only 3 schools from rural area which consists of total 145 students and the study is conducted only for class X students.
- (ii) Present study is carried out on Male and female students only. Transgender category is excluded from the study.

Method used in the study

Descriptive survey method has been used in order to accomplish the objectives of the current study.

Population and Sample of the study

The present study is based on Government Provincialized Secondary schools of Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong district, Assam. The population size of sampled institutions is 90. Out of 90, total 3 provincialized secondary schools were selected purposively for the study. A total number of 145 students were selected randomly as sample of the study among which 108 were tribal students and 37 students were non-tribal of class X. Stratified random sampling technique was used in the study.

Fig.1: Distribution of Sample

Tool used in the study and its description

Primary data are collected from field work using the Multiple Intelligence Scale (MIS-ASPS) English version, developed by Surbhi Agarwal and Suraksha Pal. This scale consists of 90 items divided into Nine Dimensions—I. Linguistic, II. Logical, III. Bodily Kinesthetic, IV. Spatial, V. Musical, VI. Naturalistic, VII. Interpersonal, VIII. Intrapersonal, IX. Existential. It was administered for collecting data on students of Class X of Karbi Anglong district who are of 18 years age. The nature of the item consists of positive and negative where the subjects were asked to put a tick mark in an appropriate box of any of the five alternative answers such as ‘Always’ ‘Mostly’ ‘Often’ ‘Rarely’ and ‘Never’. The lowest score of the scale is 90 and highest score of the scale is 450. Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test are used for analysis of the data.

Reliability of the Test

The reliability coefficient of correlations of different dimension are 0.83.

Validity

Content validity was established through expert opinion from professors specializing in psychology and measurement, Education, Sociology and English. Thus, on the basis of unanimous suggestions and agreements validated the inventory. Intrinsic validity of the Multiple Intelligence scale was also found by finding the product moment correlations among various dimensions of Multiple Intelligence.

Norms of the tool

The Z-score Norms given for all the dimension are, Mean= 244.00, SD= 66.00 and N= 200.

Results and discussion

Objective 1: To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of tribal students with regards to gender.

After collecting the primary data, the level of Multiple Intelligence of tribal students with regards to gender are categorized into high, average and low, based on the range of scores acquired by the students. As the scores are calculated, the researchers found that the overall secondary school students highest score was 340 and lowest score was 218. Therefore, the scores between 300 & above are regarded to have high level of Multiple Intelligence, while scores between 258-299 are regarded to have average level of Multiple Intelligence and scores between 257 & below are regarded to have low level of Multiple Intelligence. The results are presented below in Table no. 1.

Table no. 1
Level of Multiple Intelligence of tribal students with regards to gender

Gender	Level		No. of students
Boys	High	300 & above	10
	Average	258-299	28
	Low	257 & below	4
Girls	High	300 & above	16
	Average	258-299	48
	Low	257 & below	2

From the table no. 1, it was found that 10 tribal boys have high level of Multiple Intelligence, 28 tribal boys have average and 4 tribal boys have low level of Multiple Intelligence. The number of tribal boys with high and average level of Multiple Intelligence is significantly larger than that of tribal boys with low level of Multiple Intelligence. Therefore, it can be said that tribal boys in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

The girls Multiple Intelligence level was found as, 16 tribal girls have high level of Multiple Intelligence, 48 tribal girls have average and 2 tribal girls have low level of Multiple Intelligence. The number of tribal girls with high and average level of Multiple Intelligence is significantly larger than that of tribal girls with low level of Multiple Intelligence. Therefore, it can be said that the tribal girls in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Therefore, from the above findings it was found that both tribal boys and girls of secondary school students in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District possess average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Figure-1: Shows the number of tribal students as per different levels of gender wise distribution of Multiple Intelligence

The reason behind this finding may be the management and administration of district. Because, this district is run by Karbi Anglong Autonomous Council (KAAC) who are fully aware of the needs of tribal students particularly the need of Karbi people. The population of the district is mostly tribal people with 56.3 % as per 2011 census compared to other non-tribal people. Schools may also provide both tribal boys and girls with equal access to educational resources. Parents also equally encourage and support their children’s education, irrespective of their gender.

Objective 2: To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of non-tribal students with regards to gender

The level of Multiple Intelligence of non-tribal students with regards to gender are also categorized into high, average and low level, based on the range of scores acquired by the students. The results are presented below in Table no. 2.

Table no. 2

Level of Multiple Intelligence of non-tribal students with regards to gender

Gender	Level	No. of students	
Boys	High	300 & above	1
	Average	258-299	10
	Low	257 & below	0
Girls	High	300 & above	3
	Average	258-299	18
	Low	257 & below	5

From the table no. 2, it was found that only 1 non-tribal boy has high level of Multiple Intelligence, 10 non-tribal boys have average and 0 non-tribal boy have low level of Multiple Intelligence. Therefore, it can be said that non-tribal boys in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

The girls’ Multiple Intelligence level was also studied. It was found that 3 non-tribal girls have high level of Multiple Intelligence, 18 non-tribal girls have average and 5 non-tribal girls have low level of Multiple Intelligence. The maximum number of non-tribal girls was found to have an average level of Multiple Intelligence. Hence, it can be said that the non-tribal girls in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Therefore, from the above findings it was found that both non-tribal boys and girls secondary school students in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District possess average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Figure-2: Shows the gender wise distribution of non-tribal students in different levels of Multiple Intelligence

The reason behind this finding might be different initiatives taken by the KAAC and school aimed at promoting gender equality in education, ensuring that both boys and girls receive the same opportunities and support system.

Objective 3: To compare the Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal school students in Karbi-Anglong district of Assam.

For this objective the null hypothesis is formulated as-

H₀1. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between Tribal and Non-Tribal students at secondary level.

Table no. 3

Showing the mean difference of tribal and non-tribal students with regards to Multiple Intelligence

Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-test
Tribal	108	286.31	22.63	2.19
Non-Tribal	37	277.81	19.54	

From Table No. 3, the calculated t-value for the Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal students is 2.19, which is greater than the critical value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence it is significant. Since it is significant the null hypothesis is rejected.

This reveals that, tribal people Mean value regarding Multiple Intelligence is higher than non-tribal students. The reason behind this finding may be the dissatisfaction of the non-tribal families towards Karbi Anglong Autonomous Council (KAAC) administration. The clash between Karbi and non-Karbi people may also lead to negative attitude of non-tribal people towards Karbi Anglong Autonomous Council (KAAC). So, this kind of dissatisfaction influences directly different dimension of Multiple Intelligence.

Objective 4: To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of all boys of secondary school students in Karbi Anglong district.

Table no. 4

Level of Multiple Intelligence of all boys of secondary school students

Boys	Level		No. of students
	High	300 & above	11
	Average	258-299	38
	Low	257 & below	4

From the above table no. 4, it was found that 11 boys of secondary schools have high level of Multiple Intelligence, 38 boys have average and 4 boys have low level of Multiple Intelligence. Therefore, the majority of secondary school boys in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Figure-3: Shows the distribution of level of Multiple Intelligence of boys student

The possible reason for this finding may be the teacher follows traditional method of teaching in the school. It may often give importance to linguistic and logical-mathematical intelligence and neglecting other types like bodily-kinesthetic, spatial, musical, naturalistic, interpersonal, intrapersonal and existential intelligence.

Objective 5: To study the level of Multiple Intelligence of all girls of secondary school students.

Table no. 5

Level of Multiple Intelligence of girls of secondary school students.

★ Girls	Level		No. of students
	High	300 & above	19
	Average	258-299	66
	Low	257 & below	7

From the above table no. 5, it was found that 19 girls of secondary school have high level of Multiple Intelligence, 66 girls have average and 7 girls have low level of Multiple Intelligence. Therefore, the maximum number of secondary school girls in the Dengaon area of Karbi Anglong District have an average level of Multiple Intelligence.

Figure-4: Shows the distribution of level of Multiple Intelligence of girls student

The reason behind this finding might be girls have different learning preferences that are not always addressed in the classroom. So that, their abilities in various areas are only average.

H₀2. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between tribal and non-tribal boysstudents at secondary level.

Table no. 6

Showing the mean difference of Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal boys

Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-test
Tribal	42	283.79	25.66	1.12
Non-Tribal	11	277.27	14.10	

From the above table no.6, it was found that mean difference of Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal boys students has no any significant difference at 5% and 1 % level of significance. Hence it is not significant. Since it is not significant the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be said that parents of both tribal and non-tribal boys group might be equally investing in their children’s education, providing similar levels of encouragement, support and involvement.

H₀3. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between tribal and non-tribal girls’ students at secondary level.

Table no. 7

Showing the mean difference of Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal girls

Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-test
Tribal	66	286.84	19.49	2.19
Non-Tribal	26	276.23	21.51	

From the table no.7, the calculated t-value for Multiple Intelligence of tribal and non-tribal girls student is found as 2.19, which is greater than the critical value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence it is significant. Since it is significant the null hypothesis is to be rejected. The reason for this finding may be that tribal girls often have to involve in various family rituals, cultural activities in the society and go to paddy field for cultivation. Such kind of different activities may automatically enrich their intelligence as well as personality.

Objective 6: To find out the difference in Multiple Intelligence of boys and girls of secondary school students in Karbi Anglong district of Assam.

For this objective the null hypothesis is formulated as-

H₀4. There exists no significant mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between boys’ and girls’ students on the basis of gender at secondary level.

Table no. 8

Showing the mean difference of Multiple Intelligence between boys’ and girls’ students

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-test
Boys	54	283.83	24.51	0.12
Girls	91	284.32	20.73	

The calculated t-value is 0.12 which is smaller than the table value at 5% level which is 1.96 and 1% level which is 2.58. Hence it is not significant. Since it is not significant the null hypothesis is to be accepted. It means that boys’ and girls’ students possess equal Multiple Intelligence. The reason behind this finding may be that the teachers of Government Provincialized Secondary school in Dengaon area teach students equally irrespective of gender. The teacher also possesses the skills to teach all students following the principle of individual difference.

Conclusion

Multiple Intelligence is a new concept where every individual will be aware of different kinds of intelligence and can choose the right path and identify their own potential ability. The researchers revealed from collecting the data and using descriptive survey method that, average level of Multiple Intelligence was found on the basis of gender between tribal and non-tribal students. There are some differences between tribal and non-tribal students regarding Multiple Intelligence. It was also found that there is no difference in Multiple Intelligence between tribal and non-tribal boys, but some differences exist between tribal and non-tribal girls. In conclusion, there is no significant mean differences between boys and girls secondary school students regarding Multiple Intelligence.

Educational Implications

- i. The government school should provide for both tribal and non-tribal students, skilled teachers who can teach and make student aware regarding all aspects of Multiple Intelligence.

- ii. Special care is necessary for non-tribal students in this geographical area. Because from the findings it was observed that tribal students' Multiple Intelligence level is higher than non-tribal people. The geographical area of Karbi Anglong district is dominated by Karbi tribe and managed by KAAC. Therefore, non-tribal students couldn't showcase their intelligence.
- iii. Awareness programme on Multiple intelligence must be organized which will help students to recognize or explore their hidden talents.
- iv. Regular monitoring and evaluation should be conducted in the school. So that students maintain the regularity to promote their multiple talents.
- v. Involvement of community members should be there so that parents understand the importance of education.
- vi. The government should take strict decision to design the text books with the support of Multiple Intelligence approach

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